

INSTRUCTIONS FOR USE (EN)

OCCUR app is a "step by step" guide that was created to facilitate the process of filtering, cleaning and validating occurrence species records from data repositories. This interactive workflow will help the user in the selection of data records between all possibilities depending on their study case, considering their pros and cons. Each module will also display how data certainty and data coverage change when selecting different scenarios of the application of filtering and cleaning rules. <https://ecoinformatic.shinyapps.io/OCCUR/>

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with the OCCUR logo and a menu of modules: Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, Temporal, Duplicates, Final Report, References, and About. The main content area has a purple header with 'OCCUR app' and a 'SOURCE' link. Below the header is an information icon and a paragraph describing the app's purpose. A section titled 'INSTRUCTIONS' lists eight steps for using the app. A flow diagram shows five modules in colored boxes: Basis Of Record (blue), Taxonomy (orange), Geography (pink), Time (green), and Duplicates (purple), connected by arrows. To the right is a 'Trade-off' diagram with 'DATA COVERAGE' on the y-axis and 'FILTER STRICTNESS' on the x-axis. A solid diagonal line represents data coverage, and a dotted diagonal line represents data certainty. Both axes have funnel icons at the corners. Below the diagram is a horizontal bar representing filter strictness, with three circular icons showing the progression of data points from left to right.

OCCUR app SOURCE

i OCCUR app is a "step by step" guide that goes over 5 different modules to curate biodiversity data records. It was created to facilitate the process of filtering, cleaning and validating occurrence species records from data repositories. This interactive workflow will help the user in the selection of data records between all possibilities depending on their study case, considering their pros and cons. Each module will also display how data certainty and data coverage change when selecting different scenarios of the application of filtering and cleaning rules.

INSTRUCTIONS

1. Choose a module of the 5 available in the left panel.
2. Select between filters / steps in left-upper box (there are no previous selections marked).
3. Check the "Trade-off" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (left panel).
4. Check the "Methods" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (middle panel).
5. Check and copy the "R Code" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (right panel).
6. See the bibliography associated in the "References" panel.
7. Check how certainty and data coverage varies with each selection in the left-bottom panel to make your final selection. Values goes from 0 (minimum certainty or data coverage available) to 1 (maximum certainty or data coverage available).
8. Download the final guide to process data and write the methods section based on the selected steps by module in the "Final report" tab.

Basis Of Record → **Taxonomy** → **Geography** → **Time** → **Duplicates**

DATA COVERAGE vs **DATA CERTAINTY**

FILTER STRICTNESS

Variation in the number of records available data coverage (continuous line) and data certainty estimates (dotted line) based on precision and accuracy of records information

OCCUR app goes over 5 different modules to curate biodiversity data records.

1. Choose a module of the 5 available in the left panel.

The screenshot shows the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with a menu icon and the text "OCCUR app". Below this is a circular logo with "OCCUR" and a star. A yellow box highlights five menu items: "Basis of Record", "Taxonomic", "Geographic", "Temporal", and "Duplicates". Below these are "Final Report", "References", and "About". The main panel has a header "OCCUR app" and a "SOURCE" link. Below the header is an information icon and a paragraph: "OCCUR app is a 'step by step' guide that goes over 5 different modules to curate biodiversity data records. It was created to facilitate the process of filtering, cleaning and validating occurrence species records from data repositories. This interactive workflow will help the user in the selection of data records between all possibilities depending on their study case, considering their pros and cons. Each module will also display how data certainty and data coverage change when selecting different scenarios of the application of filtering and cleaning rules." Below this is an "INSTRUCTIONS" section with 8 numbered steps. Step 1 is highlighted: "1. Choose a module of the 5 available in the left panel." Below the instructions is a flowchart with five boxes: "Basis Of Record" → "Taxonomy" → "Geography" → "Time" → "Duplicates". To the right of the instructions is a diagram titled "DATA COVERAGE" and "DATA CERTAINTY" on the vertical axes and "FILTER STRICTNESS" on the horizontal axis. The diagram shows a solid line (Data Coverage) and a dotted line (Data Certainty) both decreasing as filter strictness increases. Below the diagram is a scale with three circular icons representing different filter strictness levels.

OCCUR app

SOURCE

OCCUR

Basis of Record
Taxonomic
Geographic
Temporal
Duplicates
Final Report
References
About

i OCCUR app is a "step by step" guide that goes over 5 different modules to curate biodiversity data records. It was created to facilitate the process of filtering, cleaning and validating occurrence species records from data repositories. This interactive workflow will help the user in the selection of data records between all possibilities depending on their study case, considering their pros and cons. Each module will also display how data certainty and data coverage change when selecting different scenarios of the application of filtering and cleaning rules.

INSTRUCTIONS

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Basis Of Record → Taxonomy → Geography → Time → Duplicates

DATA COVERAGE

DATA CERTAINTY

FILTER STRICTNESS

Variation in the number of records available data coverage (continuous line) and data certainty estimates (dotted line) based on precision and accuracy of records information

2. Select between filters / steps in left-upper box (there are no previous selections marked).

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, Temporal, Duplicates, Final Report, References, and About. The main content area is divided into three sections:

- Top section (highlighted with a yellow border):** Contains a heading "In order to validate records geographically, the user may choose what type of data needs before download (this step can also be taken after the download process by filtering the dataset)". Below it, under "Choose between:", are four radio button options:
 - Do not apply previous filters
 - Only records with coordinates
 - Only records with coordinates filtered by spatial extent (area or administrative units)
 - Only records without known coordinate issues
- Middle section:** A bar chart comparing "Certainty" and "Data coverage". The y-axis ranges from "min" to "max". The "Certainty" bar is taller than the "Data coverage" bar.
- Right section:** A "Trade-off" table with tabs for "Trade-off", "Methods", and "R Code". The table lists pros and cons for the selected filter option.

Pros	Cons
Depending on the selected area, can exclude unreliable records (e.g. zero coordinates, sea points, etc.)	Excludes records from suitable/native regions not considered by bibliography.
Excludes records from introduced distributional areas.	Excludes georeferencible records by locality information that could be repaired.
Less time of manipulation than download all available records with coordinates.	
More information available including records labelled as 'with coordinates issues'.	

Your selection:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value:
- *Recovering coordinates:
- *Detecting environmental outliers:
- *Checking coordinates precision:
- *Checking coordinates position:
- *Detecting distributional outliers:

3. Check the "Trade-off" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (left panel).

The screenshot shows the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, Temporal, Duplicates, Final Report, References, and About. The main content area is divided into two sections. The top section contains a heading: "In order to validate records geographically, the user may choose what type of data needs before download (this step can also be taken after the download process by filtering the dataset)". Below this is a "Choose between:" section with four radio button options:

- Do not apply previous filters
- Only records with coordinates
- Only records with coordinates filtered by spatial extent (area or administrative units)
- Only records without known coordinate issues

 The bottom section of the main area features a bar chart with a vertical axis from "min" to "max" and two categories on the horizontal axis: "Certainty" and "Data coverage". The "Certainty" bar is significantly taller than the "Data coverage" bar.

On the right side of the interface, a yellow-bordered box highlights a "SOURCE" panel. At the top of this panel are tabs for "Trade-off" (selected), "Methods", and "R Code". Below the tabs is a table with two columns: "Pros" and "Cons".

Pros	Cons
Depending on the selected area, can exclude unreliable records (e.g. zero coordinates, sea points, etc.)	Excludes records from suitable/native regions not considered by bibliography.
Excludes records from introduced distributional areas.	Excludes georeferencible records by locality information that could be repaired.
Less time of manipulation than download all available records with coordinates.	
More information available including records labelled as 'with coordinates issues'.	

Below the table, a dark grey box titled "Your selection:" contains a list of selected options:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value:
- *Recovering coordinates:
- *Detecting environmental outliers:
- *Checking coordinates precision:
- *Checking coordinates position:
- *Detecting distributional outliers:

 A location pin icon is visible in the bottom right corner of this box.

4. Check the "Methods" table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (middle panel).

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with the OCCUR logo and navigation options: Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, 1. Previous filters in download process, 2. Location check, 3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations, 4. Outliers check, Temporal, Duplicates, Final Report, References, and About. The main content area has two tabs: 'Use distributional information' and 'Use environmental information'. Below the tabs is a 'Choose between:' section with four radio button options: a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers, b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers (selected), c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold, and d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers. Below this is a bar chart with 'min' at the bottom and 'max' at the top. The x-axis has two categories: 'Certainty' and 'Data coverage'. The 'Certainty' bar is significantly taller than the 'Data coverage' bar. On the right, a panel titled 'SOURCE' contains three tabs: 'Trade-off', 'Methods' (highlighted with a dashed orange box), and 'R code'. Below the tabs are two buttons: 'Use distributional information' and 'Use environmental information'. The 'Methods' tab is active, showing a text area with the following content: 'Point in polygon function using range maps shapefiles.', 'CoordinateCleaner::cc_iucn', 'CoordinateCleaner::cc_outf [17]', and 'Bracatus' R package [23]'. At the bottom of the right panel, a dark grey box titled 'Your selection:' lists several parameters: '*Applying previous filter: TRUE', '*Checking coordinates precision:', '*Checking coordinates value:', '*Recovering coordinates:', '*Detecting environmental outliers: TRUE', '*Checking coordinates position:', and '*Detecting distributional outliers: TRUE'. A location pin icon is visible in the bottom right corner of this box.

5. See the bibliography associated in the "References" panel and click in 'See ref' to open the link in your web browser.

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a navigation sidebar with options: Home, Basis of Record, Taxonomic, Geographic, 1. Previous filters in download process, 2. Location check, 3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations, 4. Outliers check, Temporal, Duplicates, Final Report, **References** (highlighted with a dashed yellow box), and About. The main content area is split into two panels. The top panel, titled 'Choose between:', offers two tabs: 'Use distributional information' and 'Use environmental information'. Below these are four radio button options:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers.

 The bottom panel, titled 'SOURCE', contains a list of R packages:

- Point in polygon function using range maps shapefiles.
- CoordinateCleaner:cc_junc
- CoordinateCleaner:cc_outl [17]
- Bracatus' R package [23]

 A dashed yellow box highlights the 'CoordinateCleaner:cc_outl [17]' and 'Bracatus' R package [23]' entries. Below the 'SOURCE' panel is a list of 23 references, each followed by a 'See ref' link. The 'References' panel in the sidebar is also highlighted with a dashed yellow box. A small map icon is visible in the bottom right corner of the interface.

6. Check an example of the associated "R Code" in the table that will display with each selection in the right-upper box (right panel). Use the 'copy' button to add the lines into your R code.

OCCUR app

Use distributional information | Use environmental information

Choose between:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers

max

min

Certainty | Data coverage

Trade-off | Methods | **R code**

Copy

```
library(sf) # Point in polygon analysis
# Upload dataframe with occurrences (occData) and shapefile of administrative units (countriesSHP)

datapoints <- st_as_sf(x = occData, coords = c('decimalLongitude', 'decimalLatitude'), crs = '+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84 +no_defs')

occData <- st_join(datapoints, countriesSHP)
```

Your selection:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value: TRUE
- *Recovering coordinates: TRUE
- *Detecting environmental outliers: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates precision: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates position: TRUE
- *Detecting distributional outliers: TRUE

7. Check how certainty and data coverage varies with each selection in the left-bottom panel to make your final selection. Values goes from minimum certainty or data coverage available to maximum certainty or data coverage available.

OCCUR app
☰
SOURCE

- 👁 Basis of Record
- 🏠 Taxonomic <
- 📍 Geographic <
- » 1. Previous filters in download process
- » 2. Location check
- » 3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations
- » 4. Outliers check
- 🕒 Temporal
- 📄 Duplicates
- 📄 Final Report
- 📄 References
- 📄 About

Use distributional information
Use environmental information

Choose between:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers

Category	Value (Relative)
Certainty	High
Data coverage	Medium

Trade-off
Methods
R code

Copy

```

library(sf) # Point in polygon analysis

# Upload dataframe with occurrences (occData) and shapefile of administrative units (countriesSHP)

datapoints <- st_as_sf(x = occData, coords = c('decimalLongitude', 'decimalLatitude'), crs = '+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84 +no_defs')

occData <- st_join(datapoints, countriesSHP)
                    
```

Your selection:

- *Applying previous filter: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates value: TRUE
- *Recovering coordinates: TRUE
- *Detecting environmental outliers: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates precision: TRUE
- *Checking coordinates position: TRUE
- *Detecting distributional outliers: TRUE

8. Check the options marked in each module in the bottom-right box.

OCCUR app
☰
SOURCE

- 👁 Basis of Record
- 🏠 Taxonomic <
- 📍 Geographic <
- » 1. Previous filters in download process
- » 2. Location check
- » 3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations
- » 4. Outliers check
- 🕒 Temporal
- 📄 Duplicates
- 📄 Final Report
- 📄 References
- 📄 About

Use distributional information
Use environmental information

Choose between:

- a. Calculate environmental centroids for the species and validate outliers.
- b. Calculate environmental space for each species, check whether records overlap with it, and delete outliers.
- c. Overlap environmental information by geographical position and filter occurrences by threshold.
- d. Do not apply a filter for environmental outliers

Category	Value (approx. relative to max)
Certainty	0.85
Data coverage	0.45

Trade-off
Methods
R code

```

library(sf) # Point in polygon analysis

# Upload dataframe with occurrences (occData) and shapefile of administrative units (countriesSHP)

datapoints <- st_as_sf(x = occData, coords = c('decimalLongitude', 'decimalLatitude'), crs = '+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84 +no_defs')

occData <- st_join(datapoints, countriesSHP)
                    
```

Your selection:

*Applying previous filter: TRUE	*Checking coordinates precision:
*Checking coordinates value:	*Checking coordinates position:
*Recovering coordinates:	*Detecting distributional outliers: TRUE
*Detecting environmental outliers: TRUE	

9. Click in the Download button in the "Final report" tab to obtain your final guide to process data and write the methods section based on the selected steps by module.

The screenshot displays the OCCUR app interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with a menu. The top of the sidebar shows the OCCUR logo and the text 'OCCUR app'. Below the logo are menu items: 'Basis of Record', 'Taxonomic', 'Geographic', '1. Previous filters in download process', '2. Location check', '3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations', '4. Outliers check', 'Temporal', 'Duplicates', 'Final Report' (highlighted with a yellow box), 'References', and 'About'. The main content area has a purple header with a hamburger menu icon and the word 'SOURCE' on the right. Below the header is a white box containing the text of the final report. The report is titled '----- FINAL REPORT -----' and contains several sections: a summary of methods, a basis of record, a taxonomical check with five numbered steps, a geographical check with five numbered steps, and a temporal information filter. A green 'Download' button with a download icon is located in the top right corner of the main content area, enclosed in a yellow rounded rectangle.

OCCUR app SOURCE

----- FINAL REPORT -----

Based on the steps selected in OCCUR App, the summary of methods chose by the user to filter and clean biodiversity records is:

Basis of Record: The user will filter records to select Observations

***Taxonomical check** sums up following the steps:

1. Download option **NOT PROVIDED**
2. The taxonomical source for standardization / harmonization will be:
Type AUTOMATIC;
Spatial coverage GLOBAL;
Taxonomical coverage GENERAL;
using Matching Type EXACT
3. Selecting only records identified at a proper taxonomic rank
4. Selecting records with or without authorship information in their scientific name
5. Including scientific names classified with taxonomical status: Accepted

***Geographical check** sums up the following the steps:

1. Previous filters in download process: **Only records without known coordinate issues**
2. Location check:
 - Check coordinates precision: Use number of decimal digits of coordinates as a measure of their precision
 - Validate records based on whether coordinates values are out of a reliable range
 - Validate coordinates position
3. Correct / assign coordinates to records without them or errors from previous validations: Do not correct coordinate values
4. Distributional Outliers check: **Do not apply**
5. Environmental Outliers check: **Do not apply**

***Temporal information filter** as: Data with no temporal range using Date of collection

Finally the identification and deletion of ***duplicate records*** will be done as the combination of same species Cell Year Recorder

The user agrees to use this final report as a guide to process their data and rewrite this text to avoid conflicts due to plagiarism.

Download